

Demographic questions

- Q1. Name
- Q2. Gender
- Q3. Birth year
- Q4. Occupation
- Q5. Education
- Q6. Location
- Q7. First technological device
- Q8. Current technological device(s)
- Q9. Activity
- Q10. Daily use of technology device(s) - in hours

Close-ended questions (Likert scale)

- Q11. I know what an anti-virus software program is
- Q12. I have an anti-virus software program installed on the computer I use
- Q13. I know what a personal firewall program is
- Q14. I have a personal firewall installed on the computer that I use
- Q15. I use a password on all my devices
- Q16. What devices use passwords?
- Q17. My passwords consist of upper case, lower case, special characters, and numbers
- Q18. I do not give out my personal information (like real name, age, location, etc.) to people that I know
- Q19. I have a safe place to store my technological devices
- Q20. I do not give out my personal information (like real name, age, location, etc.) when using online gaming applications
- Q22. I do not respond to unwanted communication or messages from people I do not know (like e-mails, WhatsApp, Facebook messages, etc.)
- Q23. I have a backup copy of data from my technological devices in case those devices are lost or damaged
- Q24. I change the default privacy settings of my social media accounts
- Q25. I know how to access website policies relating to how my information is protected (e.g., privacy policy, security policy, or terms and conditions)
- Q26. I read website policies relating to how my information is protected (e.g., privacy policy, security policy, or terms and conditions) on websites
- Q27. I understand website policies relating to how my information is protected (e.g., privacy policy, security policy, or terms and conditions) on websites
- Q28. I have never been a victim in cyber space
- Q29. I will tell someone if they make me uncomfortable while interacting with them in cyber space
- Q30. I only add friends to my social networking profile if I know them
- Q31. I know where to report cyber security incidents or criminal activities.
- Q32. There are people around me who have difficulty reporting when they become victims of harassment or bullying via mobile phone or social media.
- Q33. I believe that devices such as laptops, cell phones, and tablets can be infected with viruses (malware)
- Q34. I believe that it is possible that my device can be implicated in cyber crime (this means, it looks as though the crime was committed using my device)

- Q35. I believe that criminals can access one's device (e.g., tablet, handphone) and the information on it through cyber space without physically having access to my device
- Q36. I believe if a device is lost or stolen the information could be used for criminal purposes
- Q37. I believe that it is important to back up information that is on my devices
- Q38. I believe that one's identity can be stolen in cyber space
- Q39. I believe that one's personal information can be stolen in cyberspace, (e.g., when playing online games or using various applications)
- Q40. I believe it is possible that one's bank accounts could be compromised and money stolen in cyber space
- Q41. I believe that there is risk in providing my personal information through an e-mail from an unknown entity
- Q42. I (or my friends) believe it unacceptable to post or share inaccurate or incorrect information in cyber space
- Q43. I am aware that I can be stalked (e.g., online predators, harassment, unwanted communication) in cyber space
- Q44. I believe my friends are aware that they can be stalked (e.g., online predators, harassment, unwanted communication) in cyber space
- Q45. I believe that I can be bullied in cyber space (e.g., social media)
- Q46. I believe some of my friends have experienced cyber bullying (via electronic device)
- Q47. I have experienced unwanted sexting in cyber space (e.g., via WhatsApp or Facebook)
- Q48. I believe I am safe in cyber space when doing anything that I want, as long as I stay anonymous or use a fake name

Open-ended questions

- Q49. In your opinion, what constitutes personal data?
- Q50. How important is it to protect your personal data on the Internet?
- Q51. What have you done to maintain the security of your personal data on the Internet?
- Q52. Have you experienced a crime on the Internet or had someone use your personal data without permission? If so, what was that experience like?
- Q53. Do you report if there is a crime on the Internet or if someone uses your personal data without permission? If so, how was that experience?
- Q54. What makes you feel safe or unsafe when using the Internet?
- Q55. Do you prefer to use public Wi-Fi or your own private internet connection? Why?
- Q56. What methods can be implemented to help you better understand and be aware of how to protect personal data on the internet?